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Authors

Name	Organisation	e-mail	Role
Name	Organisation	e-mail	Role
Breffní Lennon	UCC	blennon@ucc.ie	Editor/Contributor
Niall Dunphy	UCC	n.dunphy@ucc.ie	Editor/Contributor
Paola Velasco	UCC	PVelasco@ucc.ie	Contributor
Lauren Quinlivan	UCC	lauren.quinlivan@ucc.ie	Contributor

Reviewers

Name	Organisation	e-mail
Name	Organisation	e-mail
Stelios Genouzos	Witside	stelios.genouzos@witside.com
Ismini Dimitriadou	Hypertech	i.dimitriadou@hypertech.gr

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Project Consortium

Austria

- European Center for Renewable Energy Güssing GmbH

Cyprus

- Witside International Markets LTD

Denmark

- Geco Global APS

Greece

- **Hypertech** (Project Coordinator)
- Ethniko Kentro Erevnas Kai Technologikis Anaptyxis
- Mytilinaios Anonimi Etaireia
- QUE Technologies Kefalaiiouchiki Etaireia

Ireland

- University College Cork
National University of Ireland, Cork

Italy

- Rina Consulting SPA

Netherlands

- Bedrijfsbureau Energie Samen BV
- Cooperatief Energie Dienstenbedrijfs Rivierenland BA

Spain

- My Energia Oner SL
- La Solar Energia Sociedad Cooperativa
- Fundacion Undacion Circe Centre De Investigacion de Recursos Y Consumos Energeticos
- Viesgo Distribucion Electrica SL

Switzerland

- Azienda Elettrica Di Massagno SA

Executive Summary

This deliverable reports on work undertaken for Task 3.3 of work package 3 of the ACCEPT H2020 project and examines the governance and socio-political contexts that condition and structure current pathways to participation, particularly in terms of citizen energy community (CEC) formation. Applying a multi-level perspective, the authors analysed the barriers and drivers to development at a number of scales including the local/individual, regional, national, and EU levels, outlining how citizens are encouraged to, or indeed dissuaded from, participate in these types of energy transition pathways. From this comparative work, we were able to develop a typology of key drivers and barriers to citizen participation in CECs, many of which are common across member states. This is presented in Tables 1 and 2 below and is discussed in more detail in Section 5 of the report. This typology is now informing ongoing work in work package 3 and is contributing to preparatory work for work package 8.

Table 1 Governance and socio-political factors that condition citizen engagement in CECs

Uncertainty and change in renewable energy policies	Regulatory gaps, inconsistencies, complicated tax rules, and changing regulations such as the closure of Feed-in Tariff (FIT) schemes.
Lack of institutional support	Non-recognition of CECs as legal identities, changing conditions from regulators, and complex administrative procedures related to planning permissions.
Limited funding and access to finance	There is some early-stage funding to assess CECs technical feasibility, but projects are often stalled due to limited funding and lack of financial viability.
Lack of support for innovation	Lack of access to technical expertise, information, and data to design, plan, implement and commission a project.
Lack of organisational capacity and time	CECs rely on volunteers that have limited access to information and time for engaging in opportunities for greater capacity building.
Exclusion of vulnerable populations from projects	High initial investment and time costs make CEC membership rather exclusive and more typical of middle- or upper-class individuals, thus unintentionally ostracising a portion of society.
Lack of trust in the private and public sectors	Lack of trust in local authorities and energy developers has led to difficulties in leveraging partnerships, which are often critical for accessing funding and knowledge sharing.

Table 2 Drivers of citizen engagement in CECs

Improved subsidy support	Increased promotion of investments in renewables by passing laws governing community and local ownership in the energy sector, introducing a mixture of grants and tax advantages to the community energy landscape.
Increased institutional support	Higher institutional recognition of time and capacity requirements of CEC members, and simplified planning processes.
Early-stage funding and access to alternative forms of finance	Funding delivered in a way that ensures early-stage funding to enable the development of innovative technologies and new business models and for project consolidation.
Better information and knowledge sharing	Greater attention to delivering capacity building such as advice, one-stop-shops, learning about new business models, and technical knowledge to allow communities to make informed decisions and access new opportunities.
Increasing local cohesion and sense of community	Promote policies that strengthen local cohesiveness and interpersonal trust within communities to increase citizens' willingness to contribute to the community and participate in CECs.
Fostering new partnerships	Supporting partnerships among citizens, government, local authorities, industry organisations, and commercial developers to overcome technical and funding barriers.

Support new technical innovations and alternative business models

Look into flexibility services and emerging new approaches to energy production, transfer, and consumption. Innovations include battery storage, demand side management (DSM), demand side response (DSR), flexibility services, peer-to-peer (P2P) energy trading, vehicle to grid (V2G), smart grids and energy systems.

This report should be viewed in conjunction with its companion deliverable, D3.6 Report on existing European energy communities and success factors, which presents a number of the case studies that inform this deliverable. Tasks 3.2 and 3.3 ran concurrently and work within each task informed the approach taken in the other, while at the same time focusing on specific aspects of community energy participation and citizen engagement relevant to each task. While task 3.2 comprised a desk study of citizen energy communities across fourteen European countries using illustrative examples of the types of initiatives currently in place, task 3.3 focused on the drivers that influence and impact efforts made by those citizens engaged in the types of initiatives highlighted in D3.6. The authors refer to citizen engagement more so than consumer engagement because it is in their role as citizens, not consumers, that people make active choices to (dis)engage in such activities. As consumers, they are usually limited to choosing from Choice A or Choice B, but it is in their role as citizens that they are really able to engage, participate, promote, protest, vote, invest, or join in a community energy initiative.

Glossary

CEC	Citizen Energy Community
EFI	Economic and financial incentives
EU	European Union
IEMD	Internal Electricity Market Directive
NGO	Non-governmental organisation
REC	Renewable Energy Community
RED	Renewable Energy Directive
RES	Renewable Energy Source
RES-E	Renewable energy source - electricity
SME	Small and medium sized enterprise

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1. Introduction

1.1. Scope and objectives of the task

The primary goal of task 3.3 has been to examine the governance and socio-political contexts that condition and structure current pathways to participation in Europe’s energy transition. Applying a multi-level perspective, the authors of this report analysed how the intersecting governance and socio-political drivers of consumer engagement inform current citizen energy (CEC) formation. By examining these drivers at a number of levels - local/individual, regional, national and EU – the task has been to outline exactly how citizens are encouraged, or indeed dissuaded, to participate in the energy transition. This report should be considered alongside its companion deliverable *D3.6 Report on existing European energy communities and success factors*, which presents a number of the case studies that inform this deliverable. Tasks 3.2 and 3.3 ran concurrently and work within each task informed the approach taken in the other, while at the same time focusing on specific aspects of community energy participation and citizen engagement. While task 3.2 comprised a desk study of citizen energy communities across fourteen European countries using illustrative examples of the types of initiatives currently in place, task 3.3 focused on the drivers that influence and impacted on the efforts made by those citizens engaged in the types of initiatives highlighted in D3.6. The authors refer to citizen engagement more so than consumer engagement because it is in their role as citizens, not consumers, that people make active choices to (dis)engage in such activities. As consumers, they are usually limited to choosing from Choice A or Choice B, but it is in their role as citizens that they are really able to engage, participate, promote, protest, vote, invest, or join in a community energy initiative. This deliverable, therefore, will present the findings from activities in task 3.3 and provide a multi-level analysis of CEC formation as it has developed to date.

1.2. Structure

In this report, notable examples of established citizen energy communities (CECs) will be examined and outlined, focusing on their successes, limitations, and potential innovations and as they are framed by combinations of underlying socio-economic, socio-cultural and geographic factors. The report is divided into five sections as outlined below:

- This first introductory section presents an overview of the report, details the background to the work, provides context for the task undertaken, and presents the structure of the document.
- The second section outlines the research methodology undertaken during the task, detailing the research philosophy adopted and describes the research methods adopted for data collection and analysis.
- The third section discusses the socio-political contexts to citizen participation in CEC formation and provides an overview of the types of legislative supports and barriers those setting up a CEC may face at the EU, national, regional, and local levels.
- The fourth section draws on the experiences and feedback from participants to the questionnaire, which gathered the perceptions and experiences of participants recruited from within the ACCEPT consortium, and compares them to findings from the literature in the previous section.
- The fifth section then draws on section three and four together to provide a typology of the barriers and drivers to citizen participation in CEC formation both in general terms and more specifically to the ACCEPT H2020 project.
- The final section comprises a conclusion, providing a summary of the key findings and recommendations to be incorporated in ACCEPT within the wider WP3 work plan.

1.3. Interdependencies with other tasks and deliverables

This deliverable should be viewed as a companion deliverable to *D3.6 Report on Existing European Energy Communities and Success Factors* of the ACCEPT H2020 project. Taken together, both deliverables inform the approach being taken in the co-creation processes undertaken in tasks 3.1 and 3.4. In addition, they will provide a theoretical and conceptual foundation to work planned for Task 8.4 which deliberates on the participatory methods trialled in the project. The two deliverables also contribute to the partners ongoing participation in Task 10.2 on “Synergies building & collaboration with other H2020 projects” and UCC contributions to the Energy Communities Working Group of the BRIDGE initiative.

2. Methodology

2.1. Introduction

The work presented in this report primarily comprised of both desk-based research, involving a detailed literature review, and supplemented with a targeted survey focusing on the perceptions and experiences of participants recruited from within the ACCEPT consortium and the wider networks of its partners. As with its cognate report, Deliverable 3.6, an initial scoping exercise was carried out to identify the key drivers that have impacted CEC formation across Europe. The research involved identifying and analysing data from existing literature – principally from academic research databases, and ‘grey literature’ such as documents capturing contemporary politico-legal themes and reports from non-governmental organisations NGOs, national and local government, and supranational bodies like the European Commission. Assessing the extent of existing research, as well as the knowledge, theories, and practice-based analyses that are already in the public domain provides the foundations from which researchers can develop new knowledges, theories, insights, and approaches and ultimately potentially open new fields of research as a core component of the research process participation in community energy projects. To do this, the authors reviewed the growing body of literature on the community energy sector and the impact legal definitions such as CECs and RECs are having on wider efforts to drive the energy transition forward. Given tasks 3.2 and 3.3 ran concurrently, there was some overlap with some of the literature. Also, work in task 3.3 informed work in task 3.2 and vice versa. For example, the case studies identified in D3.6 provided the authors with an opportunity to see how current governance and socio-political frameworks are impacting CEC formation on a practical level. They also helped us identify and match key themes participation and engagement in the literature that were then used to inform the crafting of the survey questionnaire featured in section four of this deliverable.

The crafting of appropriate questions, the correct ordering of questions, the correct scaling, and good questionnaire format are essential for accurately reflecting the views and opinions of participants (Roopa & Rani, 2012). The selection criteria and subsequent analysis of the respondents’ answers also involved a rigorous thematic analysis, which identified common themes reflected in the literature and the more specific experiences of the participants. Thematic analysis is widely used in qualitative research in order to understand and appropriately represent the experiences of people as they encounter, engage with and live those experiences (Elliott *et al.*, 1999; in Bowen *et al.*, 2012). For many qualitative researchers, thematic analysis is a qualitative research method in its own right – as it provides the key skills for identifying, analysing, organising, describing, and reporting on the key themes from the data they engage with (Braun & Clarke, 2006; Nowell *et al.*, 2017). Also, as a process for encoding qualitative information, it can be thought of as a useful tool for translating the language of qualitative research and the language of quantitative research into an impactful mix-methods approach (Boyatzis, 1998).

As a companion document, the literature review conducted for this report was undertaken in tandem with the literature review that informs Deliverable 3.6¹, which sets out to understand the drivers and motivations of citizens as they engage with the energy system, most often in their role as consumers.

2.2. Literature Review

Literature reviews exist on a continuum from highly qualitative (with little mention of statistics or research methods) to highly quantitative (with the final synthesis based on the mathematical averaging of results across various studies reported by different researchers)

(Pan, 2017, p. 15)

The importance of a thorough literature review to the research process cannot be overestimated. Whether as a means for synthesising existing research and integrating findings and analysis on a topic (Cooper, 1998)– potentially contributing to the development of new knowledge and insights (Torraco, 2005) – or to support a position taken on a specific issue, it can serve a number of purposes. Without it, however, one cannot expect to adequately understand the topic they are engaged with (Hart, 2018). Despite its obvious importance, there has been a tendency by some to dismiss the literature review process as simply a preliminary exercise, or a precursor to ‘real’ research (Onwuegbuzie & Freis, 2016), but this misses to point as to why it is needed in the first place. An open-minded assessment of existing secondary literature, recognising both the gaps and potential insights, is key to framing current research and to planning for the future. Indeed, a literature review serves as a research method in its own right. For this report, the goal of the literature review is to develop a deeper understanding of the

¹ Deliverable 3.6 Report on Existing European Energy Communities and Success Factors should be considered a companion report to this deliverable.

governance and socio-political contexts that contribute to CEC formation. This has been achieved utilising specific research methods comprising “the familiar iterative process of searching, reading, annotating, organising, summarising, analysing, and finally synthesising” the available literature on community energy (Dunphy *et al.*, 2021, p. 10). As with Deliverable 3.6, the principal sources of relevant material were found using the bibliographic databases – made available through university library subscriptions – or were available for free online, most notably in open access journals and online national and European data portals. The material selected includes academic literature, European and national government legislation, and reports, as well as research project reports. Although all major search engines identify a majority of the material that is available, as Falagas *et al.* (2008) suggest all search engines still have their strengths and weaknesses. In order to overcome weaknesses within individual databases, three search engines were selected: Science Direct², JSTOR³, and Google Scholar⁴. To ensure we captured all the relevant literature, and in accordance with best practice, we used a dual approach. In addition to the systematic literature review, we also used a ‘snowballing’ procedure from reference lists (Kitchenham & Charters, 2007).

For the database searches, we used a Boolean keyword search, which is a data mining operation that allows a researcher to combine, or exclude, terms using the ‘Boolean operators’ AND, OR, NOT to identify the most relevant material in an academic database. As with any other method, it has advantages and disadvantages. While it is flexible and allows for multiple terms to be used in combination, it can produce too many or too few results. When considering the ‘social’ or ‘human’ aspects of the energy system, the indeterminate meaning of some terms and the variability in terminology usage across energy research more generally can add additional complexity for researchers using keyword searches as part of their methodology. This divergence in meaning is reflective of the messiness of public discourse in society more generally, but also arises from the diversity of disciplines now involved in energy research, the emergent nature of much of that research and from the emergent nature of energy communities themselves (Markard *et al.*, 2012). An example of this method in practice, involved identifying and reviewing key selected articles to identify the range of terms commonly used as keywords to indicate a paper concerned energy communities, and these terms were then included in the systematic Boolean keyword search to generate further data.

Applying a robust snowballing procedure to supplement the Boolean keyword search process gives an extra research layer that helps correct any potential information gaps that may arise from the variation in definitions of key terms, minimising the possibility for relevant research being omitted inadvertently. The ‘snowballing’ process involved both ‘backward’ and ‘forward’ snowballing (Jalali & Wohlin, 2012). Backward snowballing involves identifying additional relevant articles in reference lists; while forward snowballing identifies additional research that has cited articles determined to be of relevance for the research objective. A further layer of snowballing utilises the search engine functions to identify linked research articles, as well as examining the ‘recommended’ articles suggested by the academic databases for relevance (Badampudi *et al.*, 2015).

2.3. Data analysis and interpretation

Over the past two decades the emergent field of “sustainability transitions” has resulted in a profusion of research material, including growing body of conceptual frameworks, terminologies, and language, across a range of seemingly disparate academic disciplines (Markard *et al.*, 2012). Also, the dynamic emergent nature of energy communities, the expansion of terminology and related linguistic variabilities has been further impacted by the introduction of the European Clean Energy Package (CEP) and the new legal definitions of renewable energy communities and citizen energy communities. Further complicating issues are already arising from the transposition of the two directives into the legal frameworks of individual member states, adding to greater interpretational diversity at the national level (CEER, 2019).

To account for the variability in terminology used to ascribe energy communities, articles whose subject matter specifically referred to energy communities were reviewed first to identify the range of relevant terms and descriptions commonly used as keywords. These terms were then used in the systematic Boolean keyword search. The terms identified from the initial review, and which were used in subsequent searches included: ‘community energy’, ‘renewable energy communities’, ‘clean energy communities’, ‘citizen energy communities’, ‘energy cooperatives’, ‘sustainable communities’, ‘local energy communities’ and ‘community energy’. Secondary terms such as ‘demand response’ and ‘energy storage’ were also used to identify relevant studies.

² www.sciencedirect.com

³ www.jstor.org

⁴ scholar.google.com

Data analysis in such a growing and diverse field of research brings specific challenges. In addition to the desk-based research, which allowed for the establishing of a detailed knowledge of the governance and socio-political frameworks that impact CEC formation in Europe, a targeted survey questionnaire was utilised to capture the experiences of consortium partners and participants from their wider networks. This questionnaire was not designed to capture a representative sample of the community energy experience, but rather was designed to act as a reflective piece of research whereby the lived experiences of participants could be compared and contrasted with wider experiences identified in the literature. The survey also served as a user-oriented evaluation of existing governance structures on community energy, with the questionnaire comprising a series of open-ended questions which required participants to carefully consider what was being asked. This was done in an effort not to lead the participants down any one specific line of questioning but rather to allow participants to articulate their experiences and views in their own language. Though this approach is not without its tensions and dilemmas (Dahler-Larsen, 2018). For example, are participants to be understood as customers, clients, citizens, protesters, or consumers? Depending on their behaviours or practices they engage in at a given time, their role may change or even occupy several different roles at the same time. Therefore, the survey questionnaire was informed by participatory approaches, which try to take into account the different lived experiences of participants. This resulted in some participants reflecting on the process as being overly time-consuming, while others enjoyed the opportunity to be given 'the space' to express their own viewpoints.

In interpreting the data, both from the literature review and from the survey questionnaire, the authors integrated a thematic analysis approach. Thematic analysis is similar to the data analysis process for conducting a grounded theory approach to the research (Chapman *et al.*, 2015) and involves familiarising oneself with the data; generating initial codes; searching for themes; reviewing the themes; and defining and naming the themes (Bowen *et al.*, 2012). This iterative, two-step approach had the added effect of strengthening the review of the applicable literature and the empirical work that was conducted for task 3.3.

3. The socio-political contexts to participation

3.1. Introduction

To meet the targets set out in the 2015 UNFCCC Paris Agreement on Climate Change, RES electricity will have to play a far greater role in the future of the energy sector. At present, existing electricity grid technologies are only able to accommodate between 20% and 40% of energy from renewable sources, requiring adaptation and innovation in new grid designs in order to encourage a greater share of renewables (Bruckner *et al.*, 2014; Martinot, 2016). In addition, the Energy Transition requires far greater participation from citizens than has heretofore been the case. The transition process itself has been aided by a growing awareness on the part of customers with regards to energy-related issues, as well as technological advances across a number of key areas including batteries, electric vehicles, smart metres, demand response technologies, etc. (Eurelectric, 2019). These advancements in technology, particularly the increasing accessibility of renewable energy installations, have been identified as a key element driving the emergence of energy communities worldwide (Gui & MacGill, 2018). The consumer co-ownership in renewable energy model which is applied in many energy communities is now regarded as an essential cornerstone to the overall success of the Energy Transition (Lowitzsch, 2019b).

According to Caramizaru & Uihlein (2020) an 'energy community' refers to any number of citizens who participate in the energy system through a range of collective energy actions. Prior to the establishment of national grids, during the early part of the twentieth century, energy communities were often characterised by their isolation and distance to each other with individual cities and towns operating their own electricity networks either through privately owned companies or municipal utilities. As Lowitzsch *et al.* (2020) attest, energy communities are nothing new. They can be seen today on islands and other remote parts of the world where access to fuels remains scarce and costly. A notable departure for the current energy transition has been the move away from highly-centralised command and control type electricity networks to mainstreaming more decentralised models of production using renewable energy that is available onsite. With this rise in decentralised RE-production, coupled with the various types of consumer (co-)ownership frameworks in place, energy communities have the potential to become a standard model in energy markets into the future.

First taking on the appearance of rural electric cooperatives in the twentieth century, the Great Recession of 2008 seems to have been a catalyst for the emergence of energy communities consisting of individuals and groups seeking more affordable, environmentally-friendly and locally-controlled energy systems (Wuebben *et al.*, 2020). Energy communities exist across the globe and remain very heterogeneous in composition and application – a recent report by Caramizaru and Uihlein (2020) identified at least 24 different approaches taken by energy communities presenting a diverse range of governance structures, activities and legal forms. Energy cooperatives, established with the introduction of renewable energy support schemes, remain the most common way in which citizens participate and/or take ownership of renewable energy though other forms like limited partnerships, development trusts, and foundations, also exist (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020).

Energy communities are often presented as having a democratising effect on power, providing members of such organisations with unique opportunities to plan, finance, own and/or manage their own energy systems and energy services (Capellán-Pérez *et al.*, 2018; Genus & Iskandarova, 2020; van Veelen & van der Horst, 2018). These communities can potentially challenge the top-down energy infrastructures currently in place and transform passive consumers of energy into active co-producers, giving the power of control and individual choice back to the people (Wuebben *et al.*, 2020). By becoming prosumers, citizens may reduce their energy footprint while simultaneously reaping the benefits of a second source of income from selling any excess production (Lowitzsch, 2019b). As energy citizens working collectively in an energy community, they can potentially impact the energy sector and contribute to the restructuring of electric power networks in a manner that provides for greater levels of distribution, diversity and inclusivity (Allen *et al.*, 2019). Community energy initiatives may be categorised in a number of different ways. From a technological perspective, initiatives may be aimed at addressing the supply side of energy, through solar and wind projects for example, or the demand side, through energy conservation measures, awareness-raising initiatives, etc. (Seyfang *et al.*, 2013). Initiatives may also be distinguished in terms of their socio-cultural characteristics, for example, initiatives that are citizen-led (e.g. energy cooperatives) versus initiatives that include citizens⁵ (e.g. government- or business-led initiatives).

In most countries across the European Union, the potential impact of community energy initiatives on the energy system has not been fully realised to date. However, the potential for energy communities to become a standard model in energy markets across the bloc can certainly be seen from recent developments taking place in a number

⁵ More often than not the roles assigned to citizens in these initiatives can be rather limited and limiting.

of member states (Lowitzsch *et al.*, 2020). In the Netherlands, for example, over 500 local energy initiatives are active today, while in Germany over half of all newly-installed renewable energy production capacity involves ownership on the part of citizens as opposed to commercial interests alone – usually in the form of individual citizen investors, farmers, energy cooperatives, etc. – contributing to almost 30% of the nation’s electricity supply coming from renewable sources (Avelino, Hoffman, *et al.*, 2014). In fact, Kampman *et al.* (2016) estimate there is potential for 83% of EU households (roughly 187 million homes) to become active participants in the energy sector. As time has progressed, energy communities have gradually begun engaging in newer forms of energy-related activity. Not only producing energy but also providing energy services, which in turn has seen a steady expansion of new business models. Traditionally, smaller-scale, citizen-led initiatives focused their efforts solely on energy generation. However, it has become increasingly common to see energy communities take on new roles as providers of energy and/or offering specific and highly-specialised energy services. The range of activities in which energy communities now engage ranges from generation, supply, consumption and sharing, to the distribution of energy, electro-mobility and energy services (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020).

3.2. Multi-level governance perspectives on CEC formation

This subsection provides an overview of the types of legislative supports and barriers those setting up a CEC may face at the EU, national, regional, and local levels. While it is by no means an exhaustive account, it does present the types of experiences CEC practitioners face on the ground, according to the literature.

Citizen Energy Communities: A Focus on European Policy

In 2015, the European Commission issued two notable communications: “Delivering a New Deal for Energy Consumers” and “On a New Energy Market Design”. Both emphasised consumer empowerment as a key pillar in the future of consumer energy policy, while also advocating for a reduction in energy costs through self-generation and consumption, and an expansion of the role of the consumer through intermediation and collective participation schemes (European Commission, 2015a, 2015b). The Commission, when designing its new energy market template, identified incorporating greater shares of variable RE sources in the grid and improving support for their deployment as key priorities, as well as placing consumers at the centre of the future energy system (Lowitzsch *et al.*, 2020). Acknowledging the challenge of addressing these key priorities, the Commission recognised the need for providing energy consumers with the right framework to allow for a successful Energy Transition – from this realisation, the Clean Energy Package for all Europeans emerged in November 2016 (Lowitzsch, 2019b).

The European Commission’s revised Clean Energy Package assigned community energy a clear status in EU and national legislation for the first time in 2019. Two separate laws, the revised Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/2001 (RED II) and Internal Electricity Market Directive (EU) 2019/944 (IEMD), formally acknowledge under EU law the rights of “energy communities” to actively participate in the energy sector. Together, RED II and IEMD introduced a new Europe-wide model for the governance of energy communities and established requirements for member states to adhere to regarding the promotion of citizen participation within the energy sector (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020; Lowitzsch *et al.*, 2020). The directives remain unique in that the revised Electricity Market Directive primarily holds member states responsible for developing an enabling “regulatory framework” that places energy communities on a level playing field with other market actors. While in RED II, the enabling framework is intended to encourage the expansion of energy communities through preferential conditions or incentives (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020; Lowitzsch, 2019b). Both directives describe energy communities whose purpose is to provide an enhanced focus on environmental, economic and social community benefits over profits, and for whom effective control over the community is limited to local members or shareholders (Lowitzsch *et al.*, 2020).

However, these directives do differ in a number of respects too. For instance, RED II refers to citizens who as prosumers also have the right to consume, store or sell renewable energy generated on their premises either individually, collectively or as part of a Renewable Energy Community (REC). While the IEMD, on the other hand, refers to Citizen Energy Communities (CECs) that operate within the electricity sector and can comprise of either renewable energy or fossil-fuel based initiatives. RECs are therefore generally considered a specific form of CEC (Lowitzsch, 2019b). As previously noted, RED II outlines a number of incentives for encouraging the expansion of renewable energy communities, thereby placing RECs in a somewhat better position by providing a catalogue of explicit rights granted specifically for them and clearly defining the principles of non-discriminatory and proportionate treatment – a particularly important feature in members states like those in Eastern Europe where RECs have not been established yet (Lowitzsch *et al.*, 2020). A number of similarities and differences can be identified between CECs and RECs. Membership in a REC is generally more restrictive, constituting natural persons, local authorities and micro-, small- and medium-sized enterprises for whom the energy sector does not constitute

their primary activity (REScoop.EU, 2019). In CECs, on the other hand, any actor, including large enterprises, can participate, as long as those engaged in large-scale commercial activity in the energy sector do not exercise any decision-making power (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020). RECs situate the control of the community to the locality of their members and shareholders. CECs lack this notion of geographic proximity. However, by excluding medium- and large-scale enterprises from being able to exercise effective control it could be argued that they also meet the equivalent of the requirement for “local” control in RECs (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020; Lowitzsch, 2019b; Lowitzsch *et al.*, 2020). RED II also requires that RECs be capable of remaining autonomous from members and traditional energy market actors that participate in the community, either as members or shareholders, whereas CECs lack the requirement to be autonomous (Lowitzsch, 2019b; REScoop.EU, 2019). This deliverable therefore examines the governance structures and typologies of citizen energy communities across Europe, including renewable energy communities, and includes fossil-fuel-based energy communities.

National-Level Legislation Governing CEC Formation and Engagement

Despite the Clean Energy Package potentially paving the way to an EU-wide legal framework, individual member states differ significantly in how they incorporate the RED II and IEMD directives into national policy and practice (Lowitzsch, 2019b). As the EU pushes for movement towards a more decentralised energy system, in which consumers and local communities play an active role, member states have the responsibility and freedom to adjust national legislation to accommodate the needs of citizens willing to participate in community energy initiatives. Sokołowski (2020, p. 304) describes the EU’s regulatory framework on energy communities as quite flexible, offered to member states as “a carrot instead of a stick”. Legislative carrots, according to Johnston (2018, p. 110) can and do have a transformative effect on the industry or activity being targeted, in effect resulting in them (he gives the examples of ethanol and solar power industries) quite literally being “creatures of legislation”. Consequently, each member state’s legal system has the potential to either steer and support or hinder and block the development of energy communities (Savaresi, 2019).

National energy policies are among the key drivers shaping the emergence and success of energy communities in recent decades, with a clear correlation between the introduction of policy support schemes and the expansion of citizen energy projects since the 1990s onwards (Hewitt *et al.*, 2019). As membership in a CEC remains voluntary under EU law, member states are prevented from imposing any regulatory obligation to join an energy community. Therefore, public tools encouraging engagement with CECs need to allow potential members to decide on their own whether to become a member or shareholder. Tools such as tax deductions for small-scale entrepreneurs who join CECs, grants to local authorities for establishing energy communities, and government strategies addressing participation in CECs are therefore the types of measures considered legitimate and allowable (Lowitzsch *et al.*, 2020). Policy tools promoting renewables such as economic and financial incentives (EFIs) have been critical in the promotion of community energy initiatives, appearing particularly appealing to citizens in member states where there has already been a strong tradition of local ownership, most notably in Germany and Denmark (Curtin *et al.*, 2017). The 1990s saw a significant uptake in community investment in renewable energy projects in countries like the UK and Germany after the introduction of feed-in-tariffs (FITs) which allowed small-scale producers and communities to earn money by producing electricity from renewable sources (Hewitt *et al.*, 2019). With the introduction of FITs, Germany saw a rise in community ownership and investment in wind power projects (Morris, 2014). At this time, the UK continued to promote investment in renewables passing laws governing community and local ownership in the energy sector, introducing a mixture of grants and tax incentives that had a significant impact on the community energy landscape there (Curtin *et al.*, 2018). In addition to policy tools provided by government, energy pricing also influences public engagement and interest in community-oriented renewable energy projects – a surge in engagements with energy cooperatives in Spain, for example, resulted from increases in electricity prices in 2012 there (Capellán-Pérez *et al.*, 2018).

To date, several member states have adopted policies and measures on citizen ownership of energy, while others are in the process of developing regulatory frameworks (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020). In Germany, CECs are recognised as part of the recast Renewable Energy Act (EEG) which defines citizen energy companies as consisting of at least ten people who are all eligible to vote and for whom at least 51% of the voting rights are held by those who live permanently in the administrative district where the project is located. In addition, no member or shareholder is allowed to hold more than 10% of those voting rights (Borroni *et al.*, 2019). Originally, the act introduced a number of preferential rules aimed at encouraging “citizen energy companies” to participate in renewables auctions. However, this has been complicated by the need for citizen energy projects to hold a permit when participating in auctions, though the introduction of investment grants may lower the barriers to participation (Tounquet *et al.*, 2019 in Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020). In Belgium, an official decree now exists for the Walloon region that recognises renewable energy communities or “communautés energie renouvelable” and the rights of citizens to collective self-consumption, while also outlining the use of specific tariffs for the use of the network, as

well as contributions to taxes and surcharges (Hannoset *et al.*, 2019). It is not uncommon now for RES project tenders in Belgium to include some aspect of citizen participation (REScoop MECISE, 2019). Conversely, in Sweden, no framework currently exists for energy communities, only measures for self-consumption. The current legislation allows for collective self-consumption within a building only when all apartments are linked to the same grid connection, but not when other connection arrangements are in place; though a 2019 government report suggests widening the bands for what is considered 'collective self-consumption'. While in Estonia, the 'self-consumption facility' can be sited in multiple buildings with surpluses shared locally or fed into the national grid (Frieden *et al.*, 2019). In Denmark, the government has established a regulatory network which reinforces the rights of citizens to participate in the energy sector by requiring wind energy developers to offer 20% of ownership shares to residents living close to new commercial wind farms. This right to local ownership has also been extended to large-scale solar PV projects (Lowitzsch, 2019a). Poland's Renewable Energy Sources Act of 2015 recognises energy cooperatives, though it is mainly focused on individual prosumers. The Polish government encourages the development of "energy clusters", which are civil law agreements between participants consisting of natural persons, local government units, research institutes, universities, and entrepreneurs, and are designed to contribute to the local economy. In the Netherlands the current regulatory framework consists of a regulatory sandbox, outlined by the Dutch Electricity Act, whereby exemptions are granted for specific initiatives around microgrids and small-scale renewables generation. Under the Dutch Experimentation Decree, local experimenters are invited to initiate projects which derogate from the former act, allowing prosumers to operate a local microgrid, access special grid tariff structures for a period of 10 years, and obtain an exemption from the supply licence requirement for supply of electricity to small consumers (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020; Hannoset *et al.*, 2019). This is similar to the UK's regulator, Ofgem, which has introduced regulatory sandboxes that allow innovators to obtain exemptions from certain rules in order to trial new products, services and business models. Only projects operated by energy cooperatives and associations are eligible to apply under the Dutch Experimentation Decree. Greece's new N4513/2018 Law characterises energy communities as urban partnerships that aim to strengthen the sharing economy and innovation in the energy sector. Among other areas, this law places an emphasis on locality as a necessary condition relating to energy projects: the creation of synergies and partnerships with the aim of implementing renewable energy projects should aim to respond to local needs, maximise local renewable resources and provide benefits to the energy community members, as well as the wider local community. It also introduces special arrangements and privileges for addressing energy issues on small islands with populations of 3,100 or less, as well as financial incentives and support measures for the development of renewables power plants (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020). Both France's Energy and Climate Law and its Energy Transition Law relate to energy communities in some manner. The Energy and Climate Law hints at the potential future recognition of "communautés énergie renouvelable" whereby entities consisting of natural persons, SME's and local authorities may exercise control over renewable energy projects which they have developed in close proximity to them. Under this law the entity should enjoy access to all energy markets and be offered the opportunity to supply the local community with energy through cooperation with the DSO (Hannoset *et al.*, 2019). Similarly, the Energy Transition Law stipulates that private and public companies and cooperative societies promoting renewables projects must offer a stake to individuals, local governments and municipal buildings on which the projects are located, as well as allowing these same entities and individuals the opportunity to participate in financing the projects (Dreyfus & Allemand, 2018).

These policy measures and targets aim to address citizen and community engagement with the energy sector. While these national instruments may certainly act as major drivers of citizen engagement, not all offer the same level of ownership rights and legal recognition granted by the Clean Energy Package (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020).

Regional Engagement with CECs

Engagement for the various types of energy communities also differs on a regional scale, both beyond and within individual member states. Energy communities are often only accessible to households that have the disposable income necessary to invest and participate in the community, while low-income and vulnerable households that are more exposed to energy poverty often experience greater difficulty in accessing energy communities (REScoop.EU, 2020). When examining the EU as a whole, geographical patterns of community-based energy initiatives may be observed which support the suggestion that the level of citizen welfare plays a role in providing the purchasing power and sufficient capital to cover the necessary investments in the energy community. It is somewhat unsurprising to see that North-western European countries have a higher concentration of community energy projects, with community energy remaining a less common occurrence in the countries of Southern and Eastern Europe. This observable pattern of member states with higher levels of disposable income displaying greater levels of engagement with the energy sector illustrates the degree of regional economic difference across Europe (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020).

Regional differences in community energy also arise due to socio-cultural factors. Putting geographical and economic factors aside, different member states and European regions are characterised by cultures which may or may not be advantageous to the CEC formation. In Eastern Europe, for example, citizen participation with community energy projects has been hampered by residual perceptions and negative connotations associated with cooperatives under previous regimes (Beckmann *et al.*, 2015). In contrast, a strong tradition of social enterprises and community ownership has existed in Northern and Western European countries for years (Simcock *et al.*, 2016). In countries like Germany, Denmark and Belgium, where these values remain high, there exists a greater likelihood of CECs emerging through collective action (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020). These countries with greater levels of engagement with community energy projects also correspond to regions with higher levels of educational attainment, another contributing factor which has been revealed in research (Ruggiero *et al.*, 2019).

Within member states, regional patterns of community engagement with energy may also be identified, albeit on a smaller scale. Research carried out by Lowitzsch *et al.* (2020) which assessed 67 best-practice cases of consumer co-ownership from 18 countries for “energy cluster” potential – and the extent to which they met the RED II governance requirements – identified nine applicable cases all of which occurred in rural areas. A number of inferences have been made for this, namely that several renewable energy technologies are only feasible in areas of lower population density. Also, two of the projects – the micro-grid project on the Dutch island of Ameland and the electricity grid on the Isle of Eigg, Scotland⁶ – are situated on geographic islands, and another two – Chile’s Huatacondo micro-grid project and Italy’s E-Werk Prad cooperative – are sited in remote mountainous areas. Self-reliance continues to have particular resonance to those living in rural environments – as opposed to urban environments where access to services is far easier – it is not surprising to see more isolated areas providing a more facilitating setting for the emergence of energy communities (Dóci & Vasileiadou, 2015; Lowitzsch *et al.*, 2020).

Local Drivers of Community Engagement

The success of community energy initiatives is highly influenced by socio-cultural factors, including those that occur at the individual level, such as intrinsic motivation, as well as those that take place within the wider locale where the dynamic interplay individuals experience every day with their environment (Avelino, Hoffman, *et al.*, 2014).

One key aspect of community energy which appears frequently in the literature is the importance of community identity or a strong sense of connection to the community in question. Local cohesiveness, it has been suggested, can be a significant motivating driver when establishing energy communities (Wuebben *et al.*, 2020) as research has shown that citizens’ willingness to contribute to the community in some way depends on the strength of the social connection they share with the community (Hoffman & High-Pippert, 2010; van Vugt & De Cremer, 1999). This observation relates back to the socio-psychological literature on collective action, which reveals that a strong sense of identification with a group fosters cooperative behaviours (Tyler & Blader, 2001), a result which is backed up by extensive work from the field and from experimental settings (Brown-Kruse & Hummels, 1993; Dawes *et al.*, 1988; Goette *et al.*, 2014). Community identity can be described simply as “feelings of attachment to the community, taking pride in the community, and having friends within the community” (van Vugt, 2002, p. 797). A strong sense of community identity is capable of mobilising citizens to act (Bomberg & McEwen, 2012; Haggett & Aitken, 2015) and may potentially result in the development of more community-oriented interests (van Vugt, 2001) and a sense of solidarity (Bomberg & McEwen, 2012; van der Horst, 2008). A collective desire to make the community “a better place” can contribute towards the success of community energy projects (Hoffman & High-Pippert, 2010), though social processes may also obstruct change if cultural identity is strongly based on the existing community and is resistant to change (Avelino, Hoffman, *et al.*, 2014). However, as noted in Deliverable 3.6, one of the greatest barriers to energy community formation is a lack of organisational capacity and time available to participants to complete necessary tasks. With CEC projects largely relying on volunteers it is not surprising that there are limited opportunities and means for capacity building, given the many other day-to-day commitments they have to contend with (Robinson & Stephen, 2020).

Contacts at the local neighbourhood level can also play a part in promoting participation and a sense of identification within the community (Hoffman & High-Pippert, 2010). Social influences, such as advice from trusted individuals in citizens’ direct social networks, have been shown to influence participation – for example, almost 30% of members of the Belgian RE cooperative, Ecopower, found out about the organisation via word-of-mouth (Ecopower, 2013; in Bauwens, 2016). The presence of a “champion” who is capable of mobilising the community during difficult times has been suggested as a prerequisite for successful community action (Avelino, Hoffman, *et al.*, 2014). Champions who display high levels of self-efficacy and are capable of mobilising the community are important for spreading

⁶ See D3.6 Report on existing European energy communities and success factors.

knowledge and skills among community members, though this is also largely depended on the social context in which participants operate (Avelino, Hoffman, *et al.*, 2014; Axon *et al.*, 2018).

As has been briefly discussed above on the regional drivers of engagement with CECs, many of the most successful community energy initiatives can be linked to socio-cultural contexts in which cooperative, citizen-led approaches to energy are strongly embedded and encouraged (Avelino, Hoffman, *et al.*, 2014). Examples of companies that emerged from such processes include Schönau EWS, the German energy company which was originally founded as part of the anti-nuclear and civil environmental movements. Also, the Dutch cooperative Texel Energie, located on the Dutch Wadden Islands, was established in a culture which has always sought to strive for islanders' independence from the mainland. While the Scottish islands' long culture of self-reliance and independence contributed to the positive response the Udney and Urry community wind projects received from local people there. These socio-cultural contexts, such a strong sense of community, can contribute favourably to motivating community members when faced with the inevitable institutional barriers, operational difficulties and disappointments experienced as part of any project.

Social and moral norms have recently been recognised as potential driving factors of participation within energy communities at the local and individual levels, and have begun to receive increasing attention from the renewable energy literature. Social norms may be described as a "person's perception of social pressure to perform or not perform the behaviour under consideration" (Ajzen, 2005, p. 118). Certainly, the research has shown that social norms can (Ajzen, 1991; Bamberg, 2003; Owens & Driffill, 2008)(Ajzen, 1991; Bamberg, 2003; Owens & Driffill, 2008). Mignon and Bergek (2016), for example, found that conforming to the behaviour of peers and hoping to gain acceptance and recognition were some of the reasons reported by citizens investing in renewable energy projects.

Once a particular way of doing things becomes established as a rule, it continues in force because we prefer to conform to the rule given the expectation that others are going to conform.

(Young, 2008, p. 12592)

Consequently, the normative effect of conforming while directly impacting the individual also contributes to the wider socio-cultural factors affecting a given project. The decision whether to accept or reject say a community-led project is not without its risks for the individual who wishes to conform and the perceived consequences of one's actions can have a strong motivating impact on one's decision-making processes (Avelino, Hoffman, *et al.*, 2014). A number of social and moral norms have been identified as contributing factors to participation within energy communities, namely the shared concern on environmental issues, interpersonal trust, and social identification with the community, and as already discussed it is at the dynamic social interplay between the individual and the wider community that can effectively encourage or discourage the formation of normative responses to change (Bauwens, 2016). Section 4.3 considers these factors in more detail and integrates the findings from the survey questionnaire into the perceptions and experiences of CEC formation by participants from the ACCEPT consortium and its wider networks, comparing their experiences to that found in the literature. As the research suggests, norm-driven and self-regarding motivations remain, to a certain extent, mutually exclusive, and result in differing levels of engagement from members with regard to the governance of organisations (Bauwens, 2016).

3.3. Governance Structures and Business Models Encouraging CEC Participation

In addition to the socio-cultural considerations, energy communities must also work with the tools available to them when setting up a CEC initiative. These include the types of business models available to energy communities and how the associated rules and obligations assigned to them may help or hinder CEC formation.

The Evolution of CEC Activities and Energy Services

The activities and energy services available to, provided by, an energy community initiative can have a significant impact on the governance structure of the CEC. In recent years many community initiatives have expanded the range of activities and services they engage with, progressing from performing more traditional activities like renewable energy generation to engaging with new business models centred around electromobility, distribution, and energy services (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020).

Energy generation remains the most popular activity for a large majority of CECs (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020). Energy generation by a community energy project usually takes the form of the community collectively owning or using generation assets but feeding the energy back into the energy network or selling it on to a supplier, rather

than self-consuming the energy produced (CEER, 2019). Some energy communities like Beauvent in Belgium may only perform generation activities, while others, like Ecopower, may undertake both generation and energy supply – through the sale and resale of electricity and gas – to customers. Ecopower in Belgium, Enercoop in France, Som Energia in Spain and EWS Schönau in Germany remain the largest supply cooperatives in Europe. Some cooperatives like EWS Schönau take generation and supply one step further, distributing energy via the ownership and/or management of a community-run distribution network such as a local electricity grid or small-scale district heating network. Electromobility services are also becoming increasingly popular across the EU – car sharing, car-pooling, the management of charging stations and provision of e-cards for members are listed among the activities carried out by community energy initiatives like Som Mobilitat and Mobicoop offering electric car-sharing services run on RES electricity. Another European cooperative enterprise based in Belgium with fifteen members across five countries, The Mobility Factory, also offers electric car sharing services to its members who may wish to access a car owned by another member (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020).

Other CECs focus on the provision of energy services like energy efficiency or energy savings. These sorts of measures are already supported by a number of community energy initiatives across the EU: Courant d’Air and Ecopower in Belgium, for example, both support their members in taking on renovations of buildings (REScoop MECISE, 2019), while other initiatives support members in energy auditing, consumption monitoring and conducting heating and air quality assessments. Financial services, energy monitoring and management, as well as energy storage and smart grid integration services, are other activities associated with CECs. Other CECs take on activities such as information and awareness raising campaigns, or fuel poverty measures, as has been the case with Energie Solidaire Enercoop in France (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020). Energy communities across the EU are continuing to thrive as innovative social enterprises in areas traditionally dominated by energy utility companies and car manufacturers.

A Diversity of Business Models

The transposition of the Clean Energy Package’s rules on energy communities, which are strongly embedded in the RED II and IEMD, requires the implementation of business models that encourage greater participation of consumers in all EU Member States. The continuous development of new business models, as described above, reflects the potential for citizen energy communities to disrupt the traditional business models which have dominated the energy sector to date (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020). Community energy initiatives now present in a diverse range of legal forms. These legal forms determine the governance structure of and control rights within a community energy initiative, which in turn influences community involvement with energy projects. Initiatives fully owned and governed by the community, for example, will differ in their governance structures and decision-making processes to projects involving shared ownership between the community and public or commercial actors (Yildiz *et al.*, 2015). It can generally be seen that the most prevalent business models supporting the investments of private individuals in renewable energy to date have tended to fall into two categories:

- a. Small- to medium-sized projects revealing more egalitarian ownership schemes, like energy cooperatives.
- b. Profit-focused, market-centred investment schemes, like closed-end funds, that attract the money for larger-scale projects, but which do not allow for investor participation in the decision-making process (Lowitzsch, 2019b)

As can be seen from these two categories, various business models reveal differences in the levels of financial investment required and participant control offered. The innovation of new business models capable of fully integrating active citizen participation, in terms of both financial and decision-making processes, into renewable energy projects is thus necessary. Current regulatory conditions typically favour larger investments in renewable energy. Consumer ownership models must therefore be supported to co-exist with their commercial competitors in order for CECs operating at the local/regional levels to succeed (Lowitzsch, 2019b).

Legal structures used for collective investments in renewable energy differ from country to country and may be linked to the country’s legislation on energy communities (see sections Citizen Energy Communities: A Focus on European Policy and National-Level Legislation Governing CEC Formation and Engagement) as well as other socio-economic and socio-cultural factors. Typical legal structures seen nowadays include common types such as foundations and charities, cooperatives and limited partnerships, as well as country-specific legal forms, like CIGALES (Club d’Investisseurs pour une Gestion Alternative et Locale de l’Épargne Solidaire) in France or community benefit societies (CBSs) in the UK (Holstenkamp, 2019).

Energy cooperatives remain the most common and fastest-growing form of energy community initiative witnessed to date, particularly popular in countries with strong traditions of renewables and community energy, such as Germany and Sweden. The structure of such an initiative is primarily focused on benefiting members of the cooperative itself – they exist as social and economic enterprises that allow citizens to collectively own and manage energy projects (Yildiz *et al.*, 2015) and exist as a symbol of democratic governance where decisions are based on the principle of “one member, one vote”. Citizens living nearby the cooperative may invest in renewables generation through the purchase of shares to finance the project (Walker, 2008) and may also be able to consume and share the renewable energy produced. The distribution of profits is limited within a cooperative, and surpluses are usually reinvested into the community, though this will depend on the main objectives of the cooperative itself. Profits may sometimes be distributed amongst members through capped dividends or in another form, such as lower energy prices (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020). The Edinburgh Community Solar Cooperative Limited in the UK, for example, was originally formed as a “BenCom” or Society for the Benefit of the Community, a type of industrial society which imposes limits on the distribution of assets and shares in order to preserve benefits for the community (Roberts *et al.*, 2014). Other cooperatives may unite to form larger networks and federations at the national and EU levels. Energy4All, a network of 27 cooperatives across the UK, is one example of this. The network aims to facilitate the establishment of new cooperatives based on past experience and knowledge-sharing. REScoop.eu is the European federation of renewable energy cooperatives, currently representing over 1,500 of the 3,500 European energy cooperatives and 1,000,000 citizens (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020). These numbers reveal the potential for energy cooperatives to become a successful model for consumer ownership in renewable energy across Europe and contribute to the success of the Energy Transition as a whole.

Limited partnerships represent another legal form for citizens’ participation in the energy sector, usually with a limited liability company as a general partner in the agreement. The limited partnership model is typically seen with larger projects requiring a high level of investment, which also influences the governance structure of the partnership – voting rights are usually proportional to the value of each partner’s share or the amount of capital invested, rather than the traditional one member – one vote principle. Limited partnerships became popular in Germany with the introduction of citizen-owned wind parks like Sprakebüll Wind Park (CO2mmunity, 2019). Community trusts and foundations are another legal form by which citizen have been known to engage in the energy sector, and happen to be particularly popular in Scotland. Trusts and foundations aim to generate social value and place a focus on using profits to increase local community development, rather than providing benefits for individual members. Typically, their funds are raised through grants and loans (Krug-Firstbrook, Haggett, and van Veelen, 2019). Scotland’s Isle of Eigg is a prime example of a community energy group working to benefit the whole community: the off-grid system provides electricity to the whole island, and is owned, managed and maintained by Eigg Electric Ltd., a subsidiary of the Isle of Eigg Heritage Trust, the community organisation which owns the island (Isle of Eigg, n.d.).

A number of other legal forms may also be observed within the context of citizen participation in energy. Housing associations, typically found in the UK, Denmark and Sweden, consist of non-profit associations aimed at addressing energy poverty by offering benefits to tenants living in social housing. An example of this includes Sweden’s Bostadsrättsföreningen Lyckansberg housing association, which produces electricity through solar energy for powering common facilities used by more than 85 tenant-owned apartments (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020). Tenants may or may not be directly involved in the decision-making process, despite living in the building where the energy project takes place, though in Denmark the responsibility for managing the social housing estate is usually placed on tenants (REN21, 2016). Non-profit customer-owned enterprises are common in countries like Denmark where they are considered preferable for communities dealing with the management of independent grid networks, like district heating networks. The Marstal Fjernvarme heating plant on the island of Ærø, founded as a cooperative limited company in the 1960s, is an example of this not-for-profit ownership model – profits generated by the company are returned to members in the form of lower energy prices. Members must be owners of properties in the town of Marstal in order to be eligible for connection to the grid and buy a share in the network (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020).

Other legal forms for citizen participation in energy include public-private partnerships, whereby agreements are struck between local authorities and citizen groups and businesses in order to ensure energy provision and other benefits for a community, as well as public utility companies, less common forms of citizen participation usually seen in rural areas. These companies are run, funded and managed by municipalities on behalf of the taxpayers and citizens (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020).

In some countries it may be difficult to identify the dominating business models for citizen engagement with the energy sector. In Poland “energy clusters” dominate the citizen energy landscape, defined as civil law agreements between a diverse range of parties. As civil law agreements, energy clusters do not have a legal personality and therefore do not run as a business activity, despite some energy clusters taking the shape of a local energy

community or micro-network (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020). Conversely, in the Netherlands no specific legal model for collective citizen ownership of energy dominates (Akerboom & van Tulder, 2019). Cooperative companies with unlimited liability, cooperation projects, foundation and public ownership of energy utilities are all models used by communities in the Netherlands to initiate new projects (Caramizaru & Uihlein, 2020).

4. Drivers for the Development of Energy Communities

4.1. Introduction

In order to better understand the social contexts to consumer engagement in energy, augmenting the desk research in both tasks 3.2 and 3.3, it was decided that a targeted questionnaire be shared with consortium partners and their wider constituent networks. This type of 'mini survey' further complements the mixed-methods approach taken in work package 3. According to Kurt Finsterbusch (1976) there are five different uses for mini surveys. They can be used to provide similar types of information as one would get from large surveys, but with wider margins of error; they can be used to assess the accuracy of expert opinion on a topic; or to assess the applicability of broader findings to a particular case; they can also be used to pilot a larger study or to further investigate/explain findings from one; and, finally, they can be used to convert survey work into what has been termed "a dynamic research instrument" (Finsterbusch, 1976, p. 118). While there are limitations, primarily their wide margin of error on point estimates and their limited opportunity to conduct multi-variate analyses, they do offer a useful tool when applied to research that is more descriptive than analytical. For task 3.3, the mini survey (see Appendix I below) provided an opportunity to investigate the perceptions and perspectives of actors familiar with CEC formation and the impacts governance and socio-political contexts have on shaping citizen participation.

Drawing from both the literature and the responses received from participants of the mini survey, the following sections examine the key themes and drivers to the development of energy communities in Europe. The participants have been anonymised and coded (e.g., first participant is Q1, second participant is Q2 etc.) in keeping with best practice.

4.2. Conceptualising energy communities

How the concept of an energy community is conceptualised and applied to the various governance levels offers scholars some interesting and novel approaches to take on the topic, including deconstructing many of its associated terminology currently feeding into the policy cycle. For example, Melville et al.'s (2017) paper examines the potential for applying a commons framework to urban energy management, focusing on a community-based trial of electricity demand response (DR) in a UK city. While acknowledging the considerable literature already available on smart grids, particularly in terms of systemic value (Crespo Del Granado *et al.*, 2016; Niesten & Alkemade, 2016), demand response criteria (Derakhshan *et al.*, 2016; Perreault *et al.*, 2015; Siano, 2014; Zhou *et al.*, 2020), issues around privacy (Majeed Butt *et al.*, 2021; Qureshi *et al.*, 2021) and community-based approaches (Malik *et al.*, 2020; Morsali *et al.*, 2020; van Summeren *et al.*, 2020), conceptualising energy (particularly electricity) as a form of commons has indeed been under-theorised.

Also, Brauhnoltz-Speight et al. (2018) acknowledge that the "community" element of community energy groups is most often related to locality and a specific sense of space. Community, as Delanty (2003) suggests, is both contentious and contested in terms of how it is represented and interpreted by different stakeholders. As a term, it has had a long history and has been used for numerous ideological and rhetorical ends, regularly utilised to badge, underpin, legitimise, or popularise policy initiatives, including recently as part of broad neoliberal shifts toward reducing the size and scope of the state and offloading governmental responsibilities (Walker, 2011, p. 777). The idea of community-based – see also citizen-based – initiatives has increasingly been enrolled within carbon governance discourses and programs of recognised and supported activity. Drawing from Walker's (2011) characterisation of the various meanings applied to the term, we suggest CECs can be similarly divided into six possible iterations that also reflect the key conceptual criteria set out in the Renewable Energy Directive (EU) 2018/20017. CECs can therefore be understood as operating on several levels, including:

As an **actor** with agency that, by taking certain actions and interacting with others, allows citizens the possibility to generate, consume and store energy, while also participating in energy markets and adding flexibility to the energy system (Q1). As an actor who is concerned about climate change for instance, they use their agency to try to find solutions to global warming through the production and consumption of renewable energy (Q3), while also raising local awareness about the need for a transition to low-carbon energy systems (Q3, Q5). At the same time, these solutions provide other social benefits at the community level (Q5) such as electrification for remote populations (Q7) and energy measures to live more comfortably (Q9).

⁷ Discussed in Deliverable 3.6 Report on existing European energy communities and success factors.

As **scale**, CECs can be seen as located somewhere between the individual and the local government, comprising the notion of a collective of citizens, societal organisations, and private actors (Q11) that is not taking part in the structures of a formal government and therefore "*can be more autonomous*"(Q2).

As **place**, or community of locality, respondents see CECs as belonging to a "*restricted area with common connection to the grid*", that is seeking to increase the self-consumption of energy (Q2).

A CEC as a **network** is formed by new relationships between different stakeholders beyond the local. These networks form partnerships between individuals, companies, societal organisations, and governments, aiming to achieve joint benefits such as optimising the energy system.

As a **process**, CECs can be seen as "*communities created with a bottom-up approach*" (Q4) involving the "*free and voluntary participation*" (Q2) of 'ordinary people' (Walker, 2011) in collaborative processes (Q5). Trust is an important element for cohesion during this process.

Finally, as an **identity**, CECs adopt ways of thinking and as such can "*be recognised as innovative cities*" or improving the image of an area such as being known as a place where "*green energy*" is produced (Q4). These identities emphasise collective interests or "*feelings of community*"(Q2) that go beyond the household and family, and potentially outside the normative narratives of the state.

4.3. Motivations for citizen engagement

Energy communities are dynamic entities with memberships that continuously evolve over time. Institutional innovations, of which energy communities can be considered, spread within societies at different rates (Bauwens, 2016), making it difficult to identify any single reason behind the success or failure of a specific energy community or a citizen's engagement with one. Recently, there has been greater interest in determining the motivations of energy community investors at both the local and individual levels. Partly to aid decision-makers in designing more effective supporting policies, recent research has begun to explore the numerous factors that influence local participation in community energy projects (Bamberg *et al.*, 2015; Dóci & Vasileiadou, 2015; Kalkbrenner & Roosen, 2016).

A number of key drivers have been recognised as commonly accepted motivations for participating in community energy projects, including social, economic, environmental and political factors (Capellán-Pérez *et al.*, 2018; van Veelen & van der Horst, 2018). Research has also stressed the importance of community identity, trust, and societal norms for establishing acceptance and/or a willingness to participate in community energy projects (Greenberg, 2014; Seyfang & Smith, 2007; Thøgersen & Grønhøj, 2010; Walker *et al.*, 2010; Wüstenhagen *et al.*, 2007). The results from our mini survey confirmed many of the motivations found in the literature and also revealed new motivations, corroborating the rapid evolution of members' motivations for joining a CEC.

A main factor driving the engagement in CECs for the mini survey participants is people's interest in meaningfully addressing the climate change crisis by, amongst other things, "*using locally available resources and minimising local pollution*" (Q4). Members have a strong drive "*to push the energy transition agenda*" (Q5). One participant mentioned that the main motivation for forming a CEC was to "*become active, to actually do something about it (climate change)*"(Q3). Previous studies have correlated environmental concern with pro-environmental behaviour in general (Fraj & Martinez, 2006), as well as a subsequential willingness on the part of citizens to participate in community energy projects (Dóci & Vasileiadou, 2015; Kalkbrenner & Roosen, 2016).

Another motivation for joining a CEC is the opportunity to establishing greater energy security, while also enjoying more regional autonomy: "*citizens are able to produce a high percentage of the energy they need in their everyday life*"(Q4), "*people now have the power to produce locally*"(Q8). "*Nowadays they (suppliers) are far away in some foreign country*"⁸ lamented one respondent, but through CECs, "*people can have their own infrastructure and decide themselves about the way electricity is produced*" (Q3). Citizens have generally left it to governments and large energy companies to resolve pressing energy-related environmental problems, though this trust and confidence in their ability to create a more sustainable energy system have begun to wane. As this happens, citizens may turn towards community energy initiatives which offer a strong social critique of established governmental and

⁸ This often has less to do with any notion of 'energy nationalism' per se, but instead reflects the experiences of energy customers and the fear that the differing governance frameworks energy companies may be subject to in different jurisdictions may result in contrasting levels of service – when things go wrong – compared to companies operating closer to the customer base.

commercial arrangements, and whose members often have more trust in their own initiative and its ability to contribute to a more sustainable and equitable energy system (Avelino, Bosman, *et al.*, 2014).

Taking part and learning from the introduction of innovative technologies and projects has also been a significant motive for joining a CEC for some (Q4, Q9). One participant explained that members have an *"avant-garde feeling"* (Q2) while engaging in a CEC. Another organisation added that by belonging to a CEC, *"we have the ability to use modern devices and installations that operate on electricity with zero operating costs"* (Q11). Similarly, research undertaken by (Bauwens, 2016) examining members of the Belgian cooperative, Ecopower, found that individual motivations to invest and participate in the energy community could be somewhat explained through the innovation adoption perspective (Bergek *et al.*, 2013). In their study, early members of the energy community were observed to attach more value to innovative renewable energy production than later members.

Other incentives for taking part in a CEC include expanding energy related services such as having access to energy advice and creating *"new skilled jobs"* (Q4) in the community, while strengthening community networks. Accordingly, interpersonal trust has been found to support citizen participation and is considered by the literature to be an essential ingredient for encouraging social cohesiveness and cooperation (Wuebben *et al.*, 2020).

Lastly, members are also motivated by the possibility of making energy cost savings or, as participants said, reduce *"the energy bill"* (Q4, Q7) in their homes. Similarly, they join CEC to decrease operating costs in their businesses *"resulting in much better financial data, thus creating available funds for growth and investment"* (Q11). CECs have also offered parties the possibility to *"participate in development and investment subsidy programmes"* (Q11), as well as acquiring access to financial mechanisms that facilitate alternative forms of investment. These results support the notion that apart from joining the CEC project based on strong community feelings or environmental convictions, members also place value on the material incentives attached to electricity supply (Bauwens, 2016).

4.4. Stakeholders driving CEC formation

Globalisation is shifting traditional understandings of where electricity is produced and how it is consumed, transforming traditional assumptions of how and where citizens mobilise to secure their access to energy. How and by whom CECs are shaped intersects with the levels where critical social, political, and economic power resides, with much of the work for CEC formation involving different stakeholders working across local, regional, national and EU arenas.

CEC projects often begin locally, in the interstitial spaces of the everyday life through which people negotiate their relationships with energy. Other CEC initiatives emerge from the workings of national or international actors who, through new regulations and awareness raising, incentivise changes in the way local people consume and produce energy. This section will consider the levels and places where stakeholders reside and discuss the roles they play and the influence they have in engaging citizens.

National governments have played the role of overarching authorities that provide the varying frameworks and funding structures needed to facilitate CEC formation (Q1), while also transposing EU directives and regulations to their own national contexts (Q2). In Greece, the Business Registry has overseen the approval of the community statute and verifies its compliance with national legislation. Tax authorities have also played a role in endorsing the incorporation of CECs as legal entities (Q5). Overall, the government in Switzerland intends to provide certainty to the electricity sector thereby encouraging investments and securing electricity supply in the country. To do so, the Federal Council has ensured the opening of the electricity market to all customers. This has allowed the decentralisation of REC production and its integration in the national market. Moreover, the federal government has recently proposed to extend its contributions to incentives that *"favour the promotion of indigenous renewable energies and make them more competitive"* (Q9), while the Austrian government recently introduced 'climate and energy model regions' that funds more than a hundred community energy projects and provides them with other types of support (Q10).

Regional authorities have played an important role in enhancing the creation of CECs in Spain by raising awareness about the importance of increasing REC deployment and through the allocation of incentives. However, participants contended that the national government and municipalities should greatly increase their efforts and take more of a lead on the energy transition to low-carbon energy. They argue that national governments are in a more privileged position to communicate the suite of advantages to forming energy communities than regional entities (Q13).

Public energy agencies have also assumed a vital role in CEC formation. In Austria, agencies provide consulting services to support the creation of energy communities, mainly providing information on how to best avoid potential

risks. In Spain the Institute for Diversification and Saving of Energy (IDAE) plays a prominent role in promoting CECs, offering detailed guidelines *"on how to develop these entities"* (Q4). Switzerland's EnergieSchweiz, a programme of the Federal Office of Energy (SFOE), aims to enhance the country's overall energy efficiency by installing energy measures in collaboration with CECs, public authorities, education, and science institutions (Q9). While in Greece, the HEDNO (Hellenic Electricity Distribution Network Operator) provides CECs with access to the energy network (Q12).

Local authorities have one of the most pertinent roles in CEC creation and pre-existing relationships of trust with municipalities have been essential to motivate citizens to participate:

"From my point of view – the local community only can be addressed by local decision makers, local energy agencies, etc. to whom people have a good relationship and whom they trust. It for sure depends how the region is structured (rural region, urban region, etc.)."

"For sure, any communication and awareness raising through politicians, media, etc. can help to bring the idea to the people out there, but local level – depending on the structure – only local institutions, decision makers, energy agencies, etc. can bring something forward." (Q10)

In Austria, local authorities facilitate the development of CECs by supervising and providing supports through the process of following national community energy frameworks (Q1). In Spain, city councils can offer initial financing for energy installations such as PV to gauge interest in forming community energy projects among its citizens (Q2). Local governors in the Netherlands have also assumed an active role in contributing to the formation of CEC projects (Q3). Local authorities in Greece have particularly helped to build and enhance the reputation and credibility of grassroots movements which have been key to subsequent CEC creation (Q5) and have built local infrastructure to facilitate their development (Q11). Municipalities in Switzerland have also contributed to motivating citizens to take part in CECs by providing access to the grid for private users and offering other types of support.

Political parties have taken on another critical role in CEC promotion. Participants explained that *"left-wing"* and *"green leaning"* parties have historically showed more willingness to support the formation of CECs, and thus have facilitated their creation when in power. Also, when political parties are in power that *"do not believe in the climate crisis"*, this has often resulted in motivating citizens to organise and counter that government's lack of environmental action (Q1, Q3, Q9).

Energy companies are also contributing to citizen efforts by assisting them in seeking funding, offering advice and sometimes novel business models to facilitate the successful operation of a CEC (Q2, Q4, Q11).

NGOs too have been a critical promoter of CECs. For instance, NGOs such as Greenpeace provide leverage for enhancing the reputation of CECs within local communities and for *"stimulating citizen participation"* (Q5). Local **citizen organisations** have also been a crucial platform for CEC formation. Often, these groups already work on environmental and well-being projects and see the emergence of CECs as a natural progression of their activities. For them CECs represent a major opportunity to *"transform their town and become an example for other cities"* (Q4).

Individuals have also adopted predominant roles in engaging citizens in CECs. Participants concur that *"crazy"* people that take the initiative and are determined to *"make projects work"* have been key for the consolidation of CECs (Q3). Community leaders, such as teachers, have also been active in raising awareness about the need for locally based projects to contribute to global sustainability and for establishing trust and building good relationships between citizens and municipalities (Q7). Furthermore, celebrities such as Elon Musk (Tesla), Barack Obama and other figures, such as the lawyer Roger Cox who sued the Dutch government in 2015 requiring they cut greenhouse gas emissions more dramatically than the authorities had initially intended, have become an inspiration for citizens taking part in energy communities (Q3).

In sum, stakeholders navigate local, national, and international spaces which, with ever greater digitalisation, have become increasingly interrelated. National actors are shaping local actions by modifying regulations and introducing financial incentives, while local actors use global forums – often provided by NGOs – as platforms to consolidate their actions while establishing and strengthening their relationships with institutions of local governance and the private sector.

4.5. Governance and socio-political factors that condition consumer engagement

Section 3.2 provided an overview of the types of legislative supports for setting up CECs in the EU and at national, regional, and local levels, as well as the related barriers practitioners experience according to the literature. Through the analysis of primary data, this section offers a brief account of the lived experiences and the main challenges that CEC practitioners face while engaging with existing regulatory frameworks.

A. Governance factors

Even though the EU's Clean Energy Package has paved the legislative way towards a more decentralised energy system, survey respondents highlighted the persistence of regulatory gaps, inconsistencies, and legislative fragmentation in their home countries, describing this situation as one of the main challenges for CEC formation.

In certain countries, CECs are still not recognised as legal identities, which is preventing these organisations from gaining access to financial supports they would otherwise be entitled to and the energy market (Q1, Q10). In Austria there is no current framework in place for regulating the formation of CECs. Similarly, even though the term energy community is recognised in law in Spain, public agencies and authorities there still need to produce a legal framework that allows CECs to become legal entities (Q12), which is a situation that is *"delaying the implementation of energy communities"* (Q13). Likewise, in Greece, *"the legislative framework governing energy communities is relatively recent (2018) and the CEC and REC concepts have not been transposed yet into Greek legislation. Hence, most of the energy communities below were incorporated under the previous definition of energy communities as transposed in national law. The transposition of CECs and RECs is underway, and the new law is currently being drafted"* (Q5).

For other countries, gaps and inconsistencies in the regulation are also acting as a barrier to CEC continuation. The Swiss legislation in 2017 implemented provisions to reduce the country's dependence on fossil fuels by approving a new energy law aimed at decreasing energy consumption, increase energy efficiency, and promote renewable energy technologies, thus encouraging the creation of CECs (Q9). However, there are still deficiencies in the new legislation. For instance, guidelines are *"forcing the CECs to be organised around a single line"* (Q8). Also, while the Netherlands has a flexible framework in place, there are still legislative gaps that trump CEC consolidation. For instance, the national energy agency is not allowed to trade in electricity. Therefore, CECs are unable to purchase batteries that might prevent imbalances in the local microgrid.

Missing or fragmented regulations are often paired with costly and complex administrative procedures that disincentivise CEC formation. One participant lamented that *"expensive and complicated administrative procedures continue to apply, despite their requirement guidelines for the introduction of simplified procedures for energy communities' RES projects."* (Q11). For instance, in Greece the government did not foresee collective energy schemes, and therefore, CECs are required to follow the *"the typical administrative requirements of companies (tax reporting requirements, associated recurring tax & legal costs, etc.)"* (Q5). While in Austria, new energy companies have long lead times, and thus, new businesses take an extended amount of time to be developed. This situation illustrates the need for a tailored CEC legislative framework at the national level that has *"competent contract points to support the establishment of energy communities"* (Q10).

Finally, the decline in the number of government incentives such as net metering in countries like Greece or Spain is limiting the foundation of small-scale CECs (Q4, Q5). In Spain there was a national expression of interest to use recovering funds for creating CECs that has not been attended to (Q4). At the same time, other subvention strategies in Switzerland are prioritising renewable energy projects yet are not penalising initiatives that are heavily dependent on carbon emissions. Furthermore, there is still a lack of awareness about CEC frameworks among local institutions (Q4), and in many countries, still an absence of political support. A participant describes how at times politicians tend to *"underplay"* new business models that allow the penetration of renewables (Q9).

B. Socio-political factors

The complexity of the community energy landscape has resulted in several intersecting challenges to the rolling out and development of energy communities across Europe. As has been discussed in previous sections, socio-cultural factors can have a huge influence on the relative success or failure of an emerging energy community. The types of factors that can promote, rather than hinder, the development of community energy initiatives i.e., strong community cohesion, cannot simply be created or planned, and often take decades to develop (Avelino, Hoffman, *et al.*, 2014). In Switzerland, energy communities have existed throughout the twentieth century due to the intersecting needs of a dispersed rural population living in remote areas of the Alps and the push for electrification

across the country. Conversely in Greece, similar collaborative activities have not been commonplace there, particularly for those projects that do not have clearly discernible economic benefits for its members.

Furthermore, even strongly cohesive communities can harbour micro-conflicts and socio-political rivalries, as many community energy projects bring together groups of people who may be new to discussing and organising their energy needs as part of a group. Though tension can also be seen as being somewhat productive when handled correctly. Bringing people together who may not have heretofore interacted with one another requires careful management but organising in response to energy-related issues can create new opportunities especially for helping citizens move away from those inherited customs that take energy almost entirely for granted or defining citizens roles in the energy system as simply consumers (Avelino, Hoffman, *et al.*, 2014). The risk of free-riding behaviour (Bomberg & McEwen, 2012) presents another challenge. The willingness of community members to participate in local energy projects can be low due to what is perceived to be an unequal division of costs and benefits, whereby both participants and non-participants benefit from the distribution of positive outcomes (Kalkbrenner & Roosen, 2016). These sorts of tensions can be identified in the history of existing communities as well as in new communities. The reality remains that the success of community energy initiatives often hinges on the ability of the community to self-govern both the project itself and its members. Identifying an appropriate business model and designing the organisational principles and policies necessary to deal with the challenges described above remains crucial to the successful operation of energy communities (Avelino, Hoffman, *et al.*, 2014).

Community energy initiatives can prove particularly appealing to the socially disadvantaged, who may benefit from being able to participate in electricity markets they would otherwise be excluded from. Vulnerable consumers may benefit from reductions in energy bills as a result of their participation and enjoy the social aspects, and local value creation such communities can bring (Saunders *et al.*, 2012). Conversely, many aspects of energy communities – such as high initial investment costs – tend to make membership rather exclusive and more typically attract middle class and/or wealthier individuals, thus unintentionally ostracising a cohort of society that could benefit most from such participation (Hannoset *et al.*, 2019). This issue raises another important question which can be raised in the context of community energy – whether grassroots energy innovations, like energy communities, can bring about the desired changes to the energy landscape in ways that are morally and socially just. Education and income differences, for example, may result in vast inequalities in the types of opportunities for participation presented to citizens across the EU. Divergences in culture, economic circumstance and average citizen welfare imply a broader geographical dimension to this issue too and is illustrated by the clear correlation between the prevalence of energy communities and the levels of welfare and disposable income present in a country – these factors are clearly more pronounced in North-Western European countries. By ignoring existing inequalities inherent in the current energy system, we run the risk of perpetuating and even exacerbating these inequalities as the energy transition progresses.

C. Market factors

Finally, two market related factors continue to represent a barrier to CEC development. The energy market is still dominated by incumbent utility companies who lobby against the further opening of spaces for electricity distribution (Q1, Q2, Q5, Q7). Furthermore, access to finance is still a key limiting factor affecting the likelihood of CEC survival, especially at the early stages of its development.

Community energy therefore remains a complex process and is impacted by a variety of governance patterns and faces numerous challenges. It is this combination of influencing factors in a particular setting that will determine the success or failure of individual energy community initiatives. Given every community is subject to a complex array of differing drivers and barriers, establishing a suitable 'one size fits all' solution or even a suite of universal operation models for ensuring success still proves inherently difficult (Avelino, Hoffman, *et al.*, 2014; Lowitzsch *et al.*, 2020). The enabling frameworks developed by member states should therefore aim, as much as possible, to tailor their responses to meeting the main barriers to community energy that are specific to their country (Lowitzsch *et al.*, 2020). Rolling out more generic adaptations and expecting positive results will inevitably result in costly setbacks and may squander public goodwill⁹.

4.6. Pathways for greater citizen engagement in energy communities

Raising awareness on the need for a transition to low-carbon energy and how "*citizens can be actively involved in this process and how they can also be affected if they don't*" (Q5) was one of the participants' main concerns.

⁹ This has already been seen in the rolling out of RES-projects in many countries, most notably in relation to wind farms.

Another innovative suggestion was to include the cost of *"pollution, illnesses, and the environment's destruction"* (Q7) in the kWh cost, setting different prices according to the way energy is produced.

Participants also highlighted the need for a better transfer of knowledge about *"how the energy system works"* [given] *"energy production, distribution and consuming is a complex thing to understand for average people"* (Q7). Simplifying concepts and *"friendly"* (i.e., accessible) explanations of terminology can be particularly relevant since *"the majority don't know the difference between a kWh and a kW"* (Q7). Ways of communicating this information should also be simply and clearly presented and use tools such as a phone app where people *"can see their consumption and production (if existing) data and also recommendations and energy tips"* (Q12). The same respondent added that the more information that is provided *"the easier it is to get people engaged"* (ibid.). Participants concluded that the media and political figures can be central actors for communicating the advantages of CECs and for raising awareness at the local level. Also, the promotion of 'one-stop-shops'¹⁰ could simplify the process and *"make them more efficient and transparent"* (Q10) for citizens.

The need for alternative business models to create new *"possibilities to use energy from prosumer neighbours"* (Q3) was a pathway mentioned by multiple participants. Examples included Peer2Peer transactions and cryptocurrency financial services like Blockchain (Q1, Q11, Q12), as well as to increase investments in distributive energy resources (DER) (Q7).

Finally, participants called for the decentralisation of the energy system. They stressed the dynamics of power between local government and the citizenry on one level and that of the state, and the importance of community-based associations as key actors to produce energy 'from below': *"we need decentralization towards resilient, self-supplying, blockchain operated and interconnected cell-like structures"* (Q1) explained one respondent, while others highlighted the need for introducing more smart grids (Q3, Q9).

Individual changes that participants are doing to contribute to a more sustainable future include the use of appliances that are energy efficient (Q9, Q12), adaptation of energy consumption patterns to periods when *"less emissions are produced"* (Q10, Q12, Q13), and prioritising greener means of transportation (Q1, Q2, Q6, Q7, Q8).

¹⁰ A 'one-stop shop' refers to any firm or business that offers many different goods or services to its customers at the one place. The term originated in the United States, when goods stores there became less specialised, offering a broad range of products to keep customers shopping with them. It is used to describe a physical building or to a company offering the goods or services.

5. Discussion

With energy communities expected to play a central role in the shift to a low-carbon economy, citizens across Europe are seeing their expected roles transitioning from that of passive consumers to more actively involved prosumers, contributing to local generation, demand response, and energy efficiency measures. Drawing from findings in Sections 3 and 4 of this report, this section outlines a typology of how consumers are encouraged to participate in the energy transition and the governance and socio-political factors that condition these engagements. This typology is by no means exhaustive, but it does cover a broad range of field-based experiences associated with CEC development.

As discussed in Section 3, energy communities can provide members with unique opportunities to plan, finance and own their own energy systems, as well as manage their energy services. By working collectively, they can restructure power networks and achieve better levels of distribution, diversity, and social inclusivity. However, the full potential of CECs has not been realised to date. Building on work by Robinson & Stephen (2020), Table 3 summarises the key governance and socio-political factors that condition citizen engagement in CECs, much of them acting as barriers to CEC formation.

Table 3 Governance and socio-political factors that condition citizen engagement in CECs

Uncertainty and change in renewable energy policies	Regulatory gaps, inconsistencies, complicated tax rules, and changing regulations such as the closure of Feed-in Tariff (FIT) schemes.
Lack of institutional support	Non-recognition of CECs as legal identities, changing conditions from regulators, and complex administrative procedures related to planning permissions.
Limited funding and access to finance	There is some early-stage funding to assess CECs technical feasibility, but projects are often stalled due to limited funding and lack of financial viability.
Lack of support for innovation	Lack of access to technical expertise, information, and data to design, plan, implement and commission a project.
Lack of organisational capacity and time	CECs rely on volunteers that have limited access to information and time for engaging in opportunities for greater capacity building.
Exclusion of vulnerable populations from projects	High initial investment and time costs make CEC membership rather exclusive and more typical of middle- or upper-class individuals, thus unintentionally ostracising a portion of society.
Lack of trust in the private and public sectors	Lack of trust in local authorities and energy developers has led to difficulties in leveraging partnerships, which are often critical for accessing funding and knowledge sharing.

The creation and continued growth of CECs still very much depends on the drive and passion of community members. However, assisted by improved government and sectoral supports, growth in this sector can be further enhanced to attract citizens who may not have the same level of commitment but would like to join or form a CEC. Finding the motivation to overcome the many barriers to viability remains a key challenge for CEC formation across Europe, especially for those operating in countries with changing or diminishing state subsidies. CECs will therefore need to continue to adapt to changing political and market conditions, devising novel approaches and innovations that prioritise the 'community-led' aspects to low carbon development (Robinson & Stephen, 2020). Drawing from this research, outcomes from the Interreg-funded LECO project, and our own work, we outline the main drivers for citizen engagement and participant in CECs at present, see Table 4 below.

Table 4 Drivers of citizen engagement in CECs

Improved subsidy support	Increased promotion of investments in renewables by passing laws governing community and local ownership in the energy sector, introducing a mixture of grants and tax advantages to the community energy landscape.
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Increased institutional support	Higher institutional recognition of time and capacity requirements of CEC members, and simplified planning processes.
Early-stage funding and access to alternative forms of finance	Funding delivered in a way that ensures early-stage funding to enable the development of innovative technologies and new business models and for project consolidation.
Better information and knowledge sharing	Greater attention to delivering capacity building such as advice, one-stop-shops, learning about new business models, and technical knowledge to allow communities to make informed decisions and access new opportunities.
Increasing local cohesion and sense of community	Promote policies that strengthen local cohesiveness and interpersonal trust within communities to increase citizens' willingness to contribute to the community and participate in CECs.
Fostering new partnerships	Supporting partnerships among citizens, government, local authorities, industry organisations, and commercial developers to overcome technical and funding barriers.
Support new technical innovations and alternative business models	Look into flexibility services and emerging new approaches to energy production, transfer, and consumption. Innovations include battery storage, demand side management (DSM), demand side response (DSR), flexibility services, peer-to-peer (P2P) energy trading, vehicle to grid (V2G), smart grids and energy systems.

Decentralised energy production in the form of community energy initiatives has been hailed as a promising pathway towards fostering the Energy Transition (Lowitzsch, 2019b). The concept of 'community energy' has its basis in discourses on sustainability, as well as the ideas of self-reliance and independence, and as such challenge existing energy structures while also highlighting the importance of good self-governance (Avelino, Hoffman, *et al.*, 2014). The institutional context within which members of energy communities interact – here referring to the formal and informal rules shaping interactions between people within collective settings (Bauwens, 2016) – has a significant impact on the formation of community energy initiatives. Driving factors at the EU, national, regional, and local scales – emerging from interactions between complex governance and socio-political contexts – continue to condition and structure the participation of consumers in Europe's Energy Transition. The movement towards a more sustainable energy system involves social transformation that is both deep and systemic, and supported by the work of citizens (Knoefel *et al.*, 2018). Community energy initiatives therefore offer the perfect opportunity to combine mutual and public interest in energy formation (Bauwens & Defourny, 2017).

As we have seen above, current energy transition trajectories still have numerous barriers that tend to offset the drivers to citizen participation – and indeed, consumer engagement – in CEC formation in a number of countries across the EU. While new legislative frameworks currently being established in member states should go a long way towards countering these barriers, experience has shown that unintended or unforeseen consequences associated with how legislation is enacted or subsequently interpreted can have a significant impact on the policy cycle, scuppering the intended outcomes for policy makers. By focusing on addressing the barriers to CEC formation presented in this report, policy makers should be better able to maximise the effectiveness of the drivers for its implementation both at the local, regional, and national scales. This requires a multi-level perspective, but also a clear willingness for action. As Howlett and Ramesh (2003, p. 5) suggest "decisions by governments to retain the status quo are just as much policy as are decisions to alter it". This is an important point to consider, given all policy extends beyond the deliberate choices of policy domain actors to what has been described as the "realm of potential choices" (*ibid.*) and subject to highly complex and ever-changing alignments between government and societal actors who (re)negotiate and align their choices through specific actions and reactions.

6. Conclusion

This report presents the work undertaken for task 3.3 of the ACCEPT H2020 project, which explored the governance and socio-political contexts that condition and structure current participation pathways for citizens engaging in CEC formation. As part of a growing body of literature on the human dimension to the energy system, it contributes to broadening our understanding of the key drivers and barriers to CEC formation across the EU. In applying a multi-level perspective, the authors were able to examine the numerous intersecting governance and socio-political drivers of consumer engagement in the literature and compare those findings with the perspectives of the participants and stakeholders who took part in our mini survey. From this comparative work, we were able to develop a typology of key drivers and barriers to citizen participation in CECs. In terms of barriers, the main disruptors to CEC formation include continual uncertainty and sudden modifications to existing RES policies, often corresponding to changes in government or lobbying on the part of existing energy incumbents, and limited access to the types of financial instruments needed to get CECs up and running. This is reflective of a wider absence in institutional supports for CECs and in terms of innovation. Another barrier at the local level is the general lack of organisational capacity even for those CECs with access to financial resources. This is partly to do with how CECs and local-specific RES projects have developed over recent years, with many organisations comprising volunteers or semi-professionals who also have other social and work-related commitments elsewhere. It is also reflective of the lack of institutional support mentioned earlier, given the absence of state-sponsored supports or training that could bolster organisational capacity in many member states. Added to this, has been a tendency up to recently to prioritise those who already have access to at least some form of social, political, and financial capital, that consequently tends to exclude significant cohorts of society, who for whatever reason do not. The ideological tendency towards neoliberal, free-market financial structuring found in many member states means that CECs often require significant levels of initial investment, which excludes all but the wealthiest from participating. While this is beginning to change, with novel business models and financial instruments coming to the fore, in most member states there is still a reluctance to allow for a greater diversity in who is able (*i.e.*, allowed) to invest.

The potential for change is clearly there however, and both the literature and respondents from our mini survey point a number of key drivers that could transform citizen engagement in CECs. They include greater levels of institutional and subsidy-related supports that foster local ownership and community-led initiatives, and not simply leaving them to operate in the market to same way as incumbent energy actors with their years of experience and accrued financial capital. Most notably, early-stage funding and access to alternative forms of finance are seen as vital to project consolidation. While better training and knowledge sharing schemes would help CEC initiatives to build their organisational capacity. This would also contribute to fostering greater local cohesion between citizens and CECs, whether citizens are actively involved or not. When information is freely accessible and transparent, and shared by trusted actors within the community, the opportunity for distrust and/or opposition become greatly diminished and instead increase the potential for fostering new partnerships across different actors in the energy domain. These can be further strengthened by prioritising supports for novel technical innovations and alternative business models at the CEC level.

To get the full benefit of the work outlined here, this report should be considered alongside its companion deliverable D3.6. With tasks 3.2 and 3.3 having run concurrently, there were a number of inter-related texts and overarching themes that were applicable to both work programmes with each task offering a unique opportunity to approach the topic from a different perspective. As mentioned throughout the report, the authors refer to citizen engagement more so than consumer engagement, because it is in their role as citizens, not simply consumers, that people have an active choice to engage or indeed ignore such activities. As consumers, they are usually limited to choosing from Choice A or Choice B, but it is in their role as citizens that they are really able to participate. This growing realisation that it is as citizens, not consumers, that real participation is possible is reflected in the EU's policy shift emphasising 'the citizen', most notably the 'energy citizen' in its more recent legislative frameworks. However, a continuing enmeshing of roles traditionally assigned to consumers and that of energy citizens has resulted in a number of socio-political factors acting as barriers to CEC formation, particularly in terms of institutional and financial supports that could bolster the organisational capacity of community energy groups

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Appendix I – Questionnaire

General points

A digital copy of the questionnaire survey was shared with potential participants with expandable text boxes provided to give each participant enough room to adequately answer the questions from their perspective. Questions were devised to be simple, precise (where possible) and straight to the point. They were also designed to be open ended in some instances, to capture a full spectrum of responses from recipients, particularly those examining individual perspectives.

Understanding the social contexts to consumer engagement in energy

1. Describe what a “citizen energy community” (CEC) means to you
(no more than 100 words)
2. Please list, and briefly explain, at least five examples of citizen energy communities in your country?
3. Please describe in more detail one of the citizen energy community examples you have listed above
e.g., how did the CEC project come about? what structure do it take? what policy/legislation (if any) was useful/important for the project initiation?
4. Briefly list and explain the roles of public agencies and authorities important to the formation of citizen energy communities in your country
5. List the local stakeholders important to forming a successful citizen energy community (from your perspective)
i.e., those persons, groups, and institutions in a local area who can either promote or act as a barrier to a CEC project
6. In your experience, what are the main motivations for participation in citizen energy communities?
7. What are the main barriers to CEC formation in your country?
e.g., this can be institutional, legislative, cultural or political
8. Briefly list and describe the types of thought-leaders whom you think can bring about change, especially in terms of the transition to low-carbon energy
i.e., those persons, groups, and institutions who are respected in the local community who tend to influence discourse and opinion
9. Where do you see differences between citizen engagement and consumer engagement in energy?
10. Reflecting on your own experiences, can you identify pathways that allow you to have greater engagement in how energy is produced and consumed?
11. If you had the power to change the energy system, what changes would you make?
12. What changes in your day-to-day life do you think are required to achieve a more sustainable energy future?